

Drought in the Middle East, Causes, Effects, and Challenges

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Abstract

The Middle East is currently in front of a continuing complex drought crisis. In addition to effects on natural resources, there were noticed in different aspects including society, and the economy, and even more on the political situation. The drought disaster in the Middle East is complicated and interdependent. It includes many factors such as weak water management, geopolitical tensions, and local weather variation.

This study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the escalating drought crisis in the Middle East. It investigates the current situation and potential prospects by examining the causes, effects, and challenges associated with it. This study also highlights the possible strategies for mitigating and adapting to the current drought conditions in the Middle East. This includes water conservation and management, planning environment-friendly irrigation systems, the use of choice water sources, and adopting drought-tolerant crops.

It is necessary to identify the causes of drought in the Middle East and to promote mitigation and adaptation techniques and methods to decrease the consequences of this challenge.

Keywords: Drought crisis, Water scarcity, Climate change and drought, Drought impacts, Drought management, Drought adaptation, Mitigation strategies.

Introduction

Warm climates are common in many parts of the world, including deserts, subtropical regions, and tropical regions (Krawchuk and Moritz, 2011). Several places in Southeast Asia, Central and South America, the Middle East, Africa, and Australia are examples of regions with a warm climate (Fig. 1). According to the United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) the region "Near East and North Africa" (NENA) which includes the Middle East and North Africa classified as desert and composed of around 60% of the total land area of the region. On the other hand, around 22% are classified as "forest" or "other wooded land (Chen and Chen, 2013).

Figure.1 World Map of Köppen Climate Classification for 1901–2010 according to (Beck et al., 2020, Chen and Chen, 2013)

Drought has been becoming worse and worse in the Middle East in recent years. The region of the Middle East is classified as one of the

most vulnerable to climate change (Fig.2). The primary problem of drought was made more complex by several factors. These are generally represented by the arid and semi-arid climate, depending on main water supplies, increased demand for water as a result of population increase, and growing requirements for economic development (Tropp and Jagerskog, 2006, Falkenmark and Rockström, 2004).

Figure 2. Middle East map of Köppen climate classification according to (Mirzaei and Aghamolaei, 2021)

The lack of surface water supplies, and low ground levels are common problems in the Middle East (SowersVengosh and Weinthal, 2011).

When there is significant water scarcity in any place, agricultural systems, and many other living ecosystems, it is difficult to supply the needs of the people (Wilhite and Buchanan-Smith, 2005). This has led to developing subjects about the workable outcomes of drought on ordinary life, the economic industry, and humans in the Middle East (Droogers et al., 2012). The effects of drought can also encompass a loss in crop yields, and livestock, an extension in water stress, and a minimization in financial productivity (Troop and Jagerskog, 2006).

Research Problem

The drought problem in the Middle East contributes to the prolongation of regional instability and the protection and exacerbation of existing social, economic, and political tensions. The region is already dealing with multiple issues including instability, political conflict, and poverty. The added impact of the drought will only exacerbate these existing challenges. The challenge lies in understanding the interrelated causes, effects, and challenges of this drought and developing effective strategies for mitigation and adaptation.

Research Methodology

A literature study was conducted, for a better understanding of the causes, consequences, and challenges associated with drought in the Middle East. Historical records are examined to trace the long-standing occurrence of drought in the Middle East. The potential consequences of drought on the environment, water management, geopolitics, and agriculture to gain deeper perspectives on the crisis were also explored. Finally, scenario studies were performed to investigate potential mitigation and adaptation strategies to the current drought circumstances.

Understanding the drought problem in the Middle East is represented in prolonging regional destabilization and protecting and exacerbating present social, economic, and political tensions (Falkenmark and Rockström, 2004, DaoudySowers and Weinthal, 2022). The place is already dealing with many and more than one challenge represented in instability, political conflict, poverty, and the consequences of drought will solely exacerbate these challenges (Breisinger et al., 2010, El Kharraz et al., 2012).

Research Objectives

Understanding the causes and effects of drought in the Middle East is crucial, and improving high-quality plans and techniques for mitigation and adaptation is the most essential purpose of this study.

It is important also to find out about additional goals to reveal the most necessary fundamental elements affecting drought in the region, together with the local weather change, deforestation, over-extraction of groundwater, and The high water demand, driven by the expanding population and increasing economic development, are causing significant challenges.

1. Causes, effects, and challenges of this drought

1.1 A long history of drought in the middle east

Drought has been a continual problem in the Middle East for hundreds of years, inflicting multiple influences on the region's agriculture, water resources, and economic system (KaniewskiVan Campo and Weiss, 2012). In the records of the Middle East, there are many examples of droughts that left a lasting effect on the region, extending back to historic

times, when civilizations such as the Sumerians and Babylonians relied on irrigation systems to grow plants and mitigate their outcomes (Gleick, 1994). In ancient Mesopotamia, irrigation canals had been used as a weapon for the duration of conflicts with the neighboring city-state of Ummah throughout the reign of King Lagash (Gleick, 2018).

In addition, between seven hundred BC and four hundred BC, several pieces of evidence had been found from civilizations such as Egypt, Persia, Babylonia, and Assyria, favoring the use of diverting rivers and polluting wells as army tactics (Gleick, 2018).

Recently, droughts and their severity have become more and more in the Middle East, mainly due to the effects of climate change, in particular, the significant increase in global temperatures leading to an increase also in the intensity of heat (Zittis et al., 2022), reducing soil moisture and increasing evaporation rates (Nie et al., 2022).

Human activities additionally over years such as deforestation and over-extraction of groundwater have led to the deterioration of water resources in the region (Bhattacharya and Raghuvanshi, 2018, El Kharraz et al., 2012).

A study by (García-Ruiz et al., 2011) determined that climate change has a significant impact on water resources in multiple regions of the Middle East, inflicting more widespread and extreme droughts and decreasing surface and groundwater availability. Studies by Waha et al. (2017) and Cramer et al. (2018) also stated that the results of climate change are exacerbated using the excessive demand for water in the region, which comes as a result of urbanization, population growth, and agriculture. Other studies by du Plessis (2023) and Grossman (2017) observed that the over-extraction of groundwater and deforestation in the Middle East has

contributed notably to the increase in drought and degradation of water resources in the region.

Finally, the Middle East's drought is a complicated issue that is influenced by both natural and human forces. The drought issue is significantly made worse by the area's arid and semi-arid environment, which has little precipitation and high evaporation rates. However, human activities such as the overuse of water resources, deforestation, and land degradation can exacerbate the effects of drought further.

1.2 The Direct Impact of Drought in the Middle East

The effects of the drought on the Middle East's economy, agriculture, water security, and people's health are extensive, affecting the economy, agriculture, water security, and human health.

The vulnerability of agriculture to drought in the Middle East is an essential issue, with dire penalties for the region's financial system (Waha et al., 2017). Thus, the loss of vegetation and livestock due to drought ought to have an extreme effect on food protection and financial steadiness in the region (Mahrous, 2019). This highlights for effective strategies to reduce the results of drought and to impenetrable the long term survival of the agricultural area in the Middle East (Waha et al., 2017).

The availability and cost of other basic commodities including food, energy sources, building materials, and many other essential components for life can also be impacted by drought. This can have a superb impact on different industries and the economic system and sooner or later affect consumers when expenditures for items and services grow to be greater (He et al., 2019, Schmidhuber and Tubiello, 2007, Instanes et al., 2016, Adams et al., 1998). This is a principal problem in the Middle East, where many

countries rely especially on importing food needs from abroad (Gleick, 1998).

Groundwater supplies, which are a key source of water for many communities, can also be affected by droughts in a lasting way. Extended intervals of dry climate can purpose groundwater levels to drop, making it difficult to get the right of entry to this fundamental useful resource in the future (Wu et al., 2020). Drought may additionally cause a direct effect on human health, mainly in communities that rely on water from natural water resources that are susceptible to drought (Mehdipour et al., 2022). Drought conditions standard in many areas of the Middle East are the essential contributing component to ordinary shortages of protected consuming water, which will increase the risk of waterborne diseases (Charron et al., 2004). Additionally, extended demand for water resources can lead to conflicts and tensions among communities in the area (SalamehAlraggad and Harahsheh, 2021).

The economic system is additionally closely impacted by drought in the Middle East, as the reduction of water availability can lead to reduced agricultural productivity, decreased industrial output, and limited tourism (El Kharraz et al., 2012, Kapoor et al., 2020). The consequences of drought can additionally cause migration, as communities in the area are pressured to search for water and different residing resources (ScheffranMarmer and Sow, 2012). The effects of drought are vast and far-reaching in the Middle East, having an impact on several aspects of agriculture, water security, public health, and the economy.

2. Mitigating and adapting to the impacts of drought in the Middle East

Addressing and adapting to the consequences of drought in the Middle East is a big challenging task that requires many different sides. Some of the strategies that have been proposed to address this issue include:

2.1 Water Conservation and Management

Effective water conservation and management strategies are crucial to reducing the consequences of drought in the Middle East (Khan et al., 2020, RachedRathgeber and Brooks, 1996). This can include different aspects such as improving effective techniques of water irrigation in agriculture, reducing leaks in water delivery systems, and reducing the demand for water in industry and other ways (Shetty, 2006, Makaya and Hensel, 2014, McDonald et al., 2011, Lazarova et al., 2000).

2.2 Drought-resistant crops

The use of drought-tolerant crops may also assist in minimizing the influence of drought on agriculture in the Middle East region (Tirado and Cotter, 2010). This consists of growing new crops sorts that can tolerate drought conditions and promoting water-saving agricultural practices (Tirado and Cotter, 2010).

2.3 Desalination technologies

This technology provides the possibility to secure a constant supply of clean water for human beings in the Middle East, even at some stage in times of drought (Tirado and Cotter, 2010). This consists of the use of reverse osmosis and thermal desalination technologies, which can be used to produce fresh water from seawater (Council, 2008).

2.4 Climate-smart agriculture

Climate-smart agriculture (CSA) includes a range of techniques that assist farmers in decreasing the consequences of climate change, including drought. CSA practices can help farmers conserve water, improve soil health, and reduce their risk exposure (Lipper et al., 2014, Taneja et al., 2019).

2.5 Rainwater harvesting

Rainwater harvesting is a process that can help communities in the Middle East conserve and store water during times of drought. This involves the collection of rainwater and the storage of this water for various purposes such as irrigation, drinking, and domestic use, reducing demand for other water sources (Altieri and Koohafkan, 2008, Misra, 2014). The ability of governments and communities to collaborate to address this urgent problem is essential to the success of these solutions, which include water management and conservation, drought-resistant crops, desalination technology, climate-smart agriculture, and rainwater collecting (Wodon et al., 2014).

Conclusion

Many indicators point to an exacerbation of the drought problem in the Middle East. It has become urgent to make great global efforts from different countries to confront In general drought issue has increased in the past 20 years due to many reasons such as climate change, water mismanagement, and geopolitical tensions. Addressing the causes of drought is critical to promoting sustainable development. In addition, cooperation between countries and political stability is mainly necessary to ensure equitable access to water resources and prevent disputes over water resources as a result of water scarcity. Action must be taken immediately to

address the drought crisis and safeguard the livelihoods of millions of people in the region. Strategies like water management and conservation, the growing of crops that can withstand drought, desalination technology, climate-smart agriculture, and rainwater harvesting are frequently used to decrease the effects of drought and adapt to its consequences.

References

- Adams, R. M., Hurd, B. H., Lenhart, S. & Leary, N. 1998. Effects of global climate change on agriculture: an interpretative review. *Climate research*, 11, 19-30.
- Altieri, M. A. & Koohafkan, P. 2008. *Enduring farms: climate change, smallholders and traditional farming communities*, Third World Network (TWN) Penang.
- Beck, H. E., Zimmermann, N. E., McVicar, T. R., Vergopolan, N., Berg, A. & Wood, E. F. 2020. Publisher Correction: Present and future Köppen-Geiger climate classification maps at 1-km resolution. *Scientific Data*, 7, 274.
- Bhattacharya, S. & Raghuvanshi, S. 2018. Challenges and remedies of water scarcity. *IAHRW International Journal of Social Sciences Review*, 6, 1101-1104.
- Breisinger, C., Van Rheenen, T., Ringler, C., Pratt, A. N., Minot, N., Aragon, C., Yu, B., Ecker, O. & Zhu, T. 2010. Food security and economic development in the Middle East and North Africa. *Current State and Future Perspective. IFPRI Discussion Paper*, 985.
- Charron, D. F., Thomas, M. K., Waltner-Toews, D., Aramini, J. J., Edge, T., Kent, R. A., Maarouf, A. R. & Wilson, J. 2004. Vulnerability of waterborne diseases to climate change in Canada: a review. *Journal of Toxicology and Environmental Health, Part A*, 67, 1667-1677.
- Chen, D. & Chen, H. W. 2013. Using the Köppen classification to quantify climate variation and change: An example for 1901–2010. *Environmental Development*, 6, 69-79.

- Council, N. R. 2008. *Desalination: A national perspective*, National Academies Press.
- Cramer, W., Guiot, J., Fader, M., Garrabou, J., Gattuso, J.-P., Iglesias, A., Lange, M. A., Lionello, P., Llasat, M. C. & Paz, S. 2018. Climate change and interconnected risks to sustainable development in the Mediterranean. *Nature Climate Change*, 8, 972-980.
- Daoudy, M., Sowers, J. & Weinthal, E. 2022. What is climate security? Framing risks around water, food, and migration in the Middle East and North Africa. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Water*, 9, e1582.
- Droogers, P., Immerzeel, W., Terink, W., Hoogeveen, J., Bierkens, M., Van Beek, L. & Debele, B. 2012. Water resources trends in Middle East and North Africa towards 2050. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 16, 3101-3114.
- du Plessis, A. 2023. Water Resources from a Global Perspective. *South Africa's Water Predicament: Freshwater's Unceasing Decline*. Springer.
- El Kharraz, J., El-Sadek, A., Ghaffour, N. & Mino, E. 2012. Water scarcity and drought in WANA countries. *Procedia Engineering*, 33, 14-29.
- Falkenmark, M. & Rockström, J. 2004. *Balancing water for humans and nature: the new approach in ecohydrology*, Earthscan.
- García-Ruiz, J. M., López-Moreno, J. I., Vicente-Serrano, S. M., Lasanta-Martínez, T. & Beguería, S. 2011. Mediterranean water resources in a global change scenario. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 105, 121-139.
- Gleick, P. 2018. Water, Conflict and Peace. *Open Rivers Rethink. Water Place Community*, 11, 33-44.
- Gleick, P. H. 1994. Water, war & peace in the Middle East. *Environment: science and policy for sustainable development*, 36, 6-42.
- Gleick, P. H. 1998. Water in crisis: paths to sustainable water use. *Ecological applications*, 8, 571-579.

- Grossman, L. 2017. Climate Change and Conflict: The Relationship Between Government Response to Climate Change and Civil Unrest in the Middle East and North Africa.
- He, X., Estes, L., Konar, M., Tian, D., Anghileri, D., Baylis, K., Evans, T. P. & Sheffield, J. 2019. Integrated approaches to understanding and reducing drought impact on food security across scales. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 40, 43-54.
- Instones, A., Kokorev, V., Janowicz, R., Bruland, O., Sand, K. & Prowse, T. 2016. Changes to freshwater systems affecting Arctic infrastructure and natural resources. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Biogeosciences*, 121, 567-585.
- Kaniewski, D., Van Campo, E. & Weiss, H. 2012. Drought is a recurring challenge in the Middle East. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 109, 3862-3867.
- Kapoor, D., Bhardwaj, S., Landi, M., Sharma, A., Ramakrishnan, M. & Sharma, A. 2020. The impact of drought in plant metabolism: How to exploit tolerance mechanisms to increase crop production. *Applied Sciences*, 10, 5692.
- Khan, N., Ali, S., Tariq, H., Latif, S., Yasmin, H., Mehmood, A. & Shahid, M. A. 2020. Water conservation and plant survival strategies of rhizobacteria under drought stress. *Agronomy*, 10, 1683.
- Krawchuk, M. A. & Moritz, M. A. 2011. Constraints on global fire activity vary across a resource gradient. *Ecology*, 92, 121-132.
- Lazarova, V., Cirelli, G., Jeffrey, P., Salgot, M., Icekson, N. & Brissaud, F. 2000. Enhancement of integrated water management and water reuse in Europe and the Middle East. *Water Science and Technology*, 42, 193-202.
- Lipper, L., Thornton, P., Campbell, B. M., Baedeker, T., Braimoh, A., Bwalya, M., Caron, P., Cattaneo, A., Garrity, D. & Henry, K. 2014. Climate-smart agriculture for food security. *Nature climate change*, 4, 1068-1072.

- Mahrous, W. 2019. Climate change and food security in EAC region: a panel data analysis. *Review of Economics and Political Science*, 4, 270-284.
- Makaya, E. & Hensel, O. 2014. Water distribution systems efficiency assessment indicators—concepts and application. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 3, 219-228.
- McDonald, R. I., Douglas, I., Revenga, C., Hale, R., Grimm, N., Grönwall, J. & Fekete, B. 2011. Global urban growth and the geography of water availability, quality, and delivery. *Ambio*, 40, 437-446.
- Mehdipour, S., Nakhaee, N., Khankeh, H. & Haghdoost, A. A. 2022. Impacts of drought on health: a qualitative case study from Iran. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 76, 103007.
- Mirzaei, P. A. & Aghamolaei, R. 2021. The Hot Climate of the Middle East. In: ENTERIA, N., SANTAMOURIS, M. & EICKER, U. (eds.) *Urban Heat Island (UHI) Mitigation: Hot and Humid Regions*. Singapore: Springer Singapore.
- Misra, A. K. 2014. Climate change and challenges of water and food security. *International Journal of Sustainable Built Environment*, 3, 153-165.
- Nie, W., Kumar, S. V., Arsenault, K. R., Peters-Lidard, C. D., Mladenova, I. E., Bergaoui, K., Hazra, A., Zaitchik, B. F., Mahanama, S. P. & McDonnell, R. 2022. Towards effective drought monitoring in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region: implications from assimilating leaf area index and soil moisture into the Noah-MP land surface model for Morocco. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 26, 2365-2386.
- Rached, E., Rathgeber, E. & Brooks, D. 1996. Water management in Africa and the Middle East: challenges and opportunities.
- Salameh, M. T. B., Alraggad, M. & Harahsheh, S. T. 2021. The water crisis and the conflict in the Middle East. *Sustainable Water Resources Management*, 7, 1-14.

- Scheffran, J., Marmer, E. & Sow, P. 2012. Migration as a contribution to resilience and innovation in climate adaptation: Social networks and co-development in Northwest Africa. *Applied geography*, 33, 119-127.
- Schmidhuber, J. & Tubiello, F. N. 2007. Global food security under climate change. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 104, 19703-19708.
- Shetty, S. 2006. Water, food security and agricultural policy in the Middle East and North Africa region.
- Sowers, J., Vengosh, A. & Weinthal, E. 2011. Climate change, water resources, and the politics of adaptation in the Middle East and North Africa. *Climatic Change*, 104, 599-627.
- Taneja, G., Pal, B. D., Joshi, P. K., Aggarwal, P. K. & Tyagi, N. K. 2019. Farmers' preferences for climate-smart agriculture—an assessment in the Indo-Gangetic Plain. *Climate Smart Agriculture in South Asia: Technologies, Policies and Institutions*, 91-111.
- Tirado, R. & Cotter, J. 2010. Ecological farming: Drought-resistant agriculture. *Exeter, UK: Greenpeace Research Laboratories*.
- Tropp, H. & Jagerskog, A. 2006. Water scarcity challenges in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA). *Human development report*, 1-26.
- Waha, K., Krummenauer, L., Adams, S., Aich, V., Baarsch, F., Coumou, D., Fader, M., Hoff, H., Jobbins, G. & Marcus, R. 2017. Climate change impacts in the Middle East and Northern Africa (MENA) region and their implications for vulnerable population groups. *Regional Environmental Change*, 17, 1623-1638.
- Wilhite, D. A. & Buchanan-Smith, M. 2005. Drought as hazard: understanding the natural and social context. *Drought and water crises: Science, technology, and management issues*, 3, 29.

- Wodon, Q., Liverani, A., Joseph, G. & Bougnoux, N. 2014. *Climate change and migration: evidence from the Middle East and North Africa*, World Bank Publications.
- Wu, W.-Y., Lo, M.-H., Wada, Y., Famiglietti, J. S., Reager, J. T., Yeh, P. J.-F., Ducharne, A. & Yang, Z.-L. 2020. Divergent effects of climate change on future groundwater availability in key mid-latitude aquifers. *Nature communications*, 11, 3710.
- Zittis, G., Almazroui, M., Alpert, P., Ciais, P., Cramer, W., Dahdal, Y., Fnais, M., Francis, D., Hadjinicolaou, P. & Howari, F. 2022. Climate change and weather extremes in the Eastern Mediterranean and Middle East. *Reviews of geophysics*, 60, e2021RG000762.